

JENSEN PROOF OF A CURIOUS BINOMIAL IDENTITY

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Abstract

By means of the Jensen formulae on binomial convolutions, a new proof is presented for a curious identity due to Z.-W. Sun.

Based on double recurrence relations, Sun [6] discovered the following binomial identity

$$S_m := (x + m + 1) \sum_{i=0}^m (-1)^i \binom{x+y+i}{m-i} \binom{y+2i}{i} - \sum_{i=0}^m (-4)^i \binom{x+i}{m-i} = (x-m) \binom{x}{m}.$$

Recently, three alternative proofs have been provided by Panholzer and Prodinger [5] via the generating function method, by Merlini and Sprugnoli [4] through Riordan arrays, and by Ekhad and Mohammed [2] based on the “WZ” method. Combining Jensen’s identity and Chu-Vandermonde convolution formulae on binomial coefficients, we present yet another proof for this result which provides a shortcut.

By means of the Jensen formulae (cf. [1, Eq 8] for example) on binomial convolutions

$$\sum_{i=0}^m \binom{a+bi}{i} \binom{c-bi}{m-i} = \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{a+c-k}{m-k} b^k$$

the first binomial sum displayed in S_m can be reformulated as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=0}^m (-1)^i \binom{x+y+i}{m-i} \binom{y+2i}{i} &= (-1)^m \sum_{i=0}^m \binom{y+2i}{i} \binom{-1-x-y+m-2i}{m-i} \\ &= (-1)^m \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{-1-x+m-k}{m-k} 2^k = \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{x}{m-k} (-2)^k. \end{aligned}$$

For a complex x and a natural number n , denote the shifted factorial of x of order n by

$$(x)_0 = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad (x)_n = x(x+1)\cdots(x+n-1) \quad \text{for} \quad n = 1, 2, \dots.$$

In accordance with the parity of k , writing $k := \delta + 2k'$ with $\delta := 0, 1$ and then performing the replacement $j := i - \delta - k'$, we can derive the following binomial coefficient identity:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\frac{k}{2} \leq i \leq k} \binom{i}{k-i} (-4)^i &= (-4)^{\delta+k'} \sum_{j=0}^{k'} \binom{\delta+k'+j}{k'-j} (-4)^j \\ &= (-4)^{\delta+k'} \sum_{j=0}^{k'} \frac{(-1)^j (\delta+k'+j)!}{j!(k'-j)!(1/2+\delta)_j} \\ &= (-4)^{\delta+k'} \frac{(1+\delta)_{k'}}{(1/2+\delta)_{k'}} \sum_{j=0}^{k'} \binom{-1-\delta-k'}{j} \binom{\delta-1/2+k'}{k'-j} \\ &= (-4)^{\delta+k'} \frac{(1+\delta)_{k'}}{(1/2+\delta)_{k'}} \binom{-3/2}{k'} = (-1)^k 2^k (1+k) \end{aligned}$$

where the Chu-Vandermonde convolution formulae has been applied.

This binomial identity allows us to express the second sum displayed in S_m as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=0}^m \binom{x+i}{m-i} (-4)^i &= \sum_{i=0}^m (-4)^i \sum_{k=i}^m \binom{x}{m-k} \binom{i}{k-i} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{x}{m-k} \sum_{\frac{k}{2} \leq i \leq k} \binom{i}{k-i} (-4)^i \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{x}{m-k} (-2)^k (k+1). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore the linear combination of the two binomial sums in S_m results in

$$\begin{aligned} S_m &= \sum_{k=0}^m (x+m-k) \binom{x}{m-k} (-2)^k = \sum_{k=0}^m \{(x-m+k) + 2(m-k)\} \binom{x}{m-k} (-2)^k \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^m (1+m-k) \binom{x}{1+m-k} (-2)^k - \sum_{k=0}^m (m-k) \binom{x}{m-k} (-2)^{k+1} \\ &= (m+1) \binom{x}{m+1} \end{aligned}$$

where the two sums with respect to k in the last line have been telescoped. This completes the proof of the identity originally due to Sun.

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